

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The following general procedure was followed for the preparation of the derivatives.

Preparation of Benzoylsulphathiazole.—Sulphathiazole (1 g.) was dissolved in 5 c.c. of sodium hydroxide (5%) and benzoyl chloride (0.6 c.c.) was added with good shaking in two or three portions. After each addition the mixture was well shaken. The product separating from the alkaline solution was left to stand for 2 hours with occasional shaking. Then the product was made acidic, and the precipitated benzoyl derivative was filtered off, washed several times with water and alcohol, dried and weighed, yield 1.2 g. Recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 250-51°.

TABLE I

R	Acid used.	M.p.	Isocyclic acyl derivatives of sulphathiazole.		Isocyclic acyl derivatives of sulphapyridine.		
			Found.	Theo :	M.p.	Found.	Theo :
C ₆ H ₅ -	Benzoic	250-51°	11.66	11.69	246-8°	11.83	11.90
<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoic	240°	10.96	10.67	238°	11.27	10.83
<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>p</i> -Bromobenzoic	263°	9.22	9.58	215°	9.62	9.72
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic	265°	14.04	13.93	258°	13.87	14.09
<i>p</i> -OMe-C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzoic	185-6°	10.64	10.80	165-6°	11.50	10.96
C ₆ H ₅ .CH=CH-	Cinnamic	253°	10.92	10.91	235°	11.11	11.09
C ₆ H ₅ .CH ₂ -	Phenylacetic	143-5°	11.66	11.26	189°	11.45	11.44
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>p</i> -Toluic	265°	11.43	11.28	197-8°	11.13	11.44

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STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART VI. N¹-AND N⁴ SUBSTITUTED SULPHANILAMIDES-AZO-DYES DERIVED FROM SULPHATHIAZOLE AND SULPHAPYRIDINE

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Twentysix azo-dyes have been prepared by diazotizing sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine and coupling with aromatic hydroxy and amino compounds.

Although it has not yet been fully proved, the opinion concerning the mode of action of the prontosils (the azo-dyes derived from sulphanilamide) is believed to be the result of the reductive cleavage of the azo-linkage *in vivo*, giving rise to sulphanilamide, which in turn is responsible for the antistreptococcal property.

Further, when these azo-dyes undergo reduction *in vivo*, they give rise not only to sulphanilamide but also to aminophenols and aromatic polyamines. It is known that these aminophenols and aromatic polyamines are oxidised in the system giving rise *in vivo* to quinonoid bodies (Tischler *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940,

62, 1881; Doisy *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, 28, 477) and further many synthetic and natural quinones are in use as antibacterial agents (Raistrack *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1941, 60, 828; 1942, 61, 22, 48 128, 485). Some quinones occur in some bacteria and in addition are known to constitute essential growth factors (Woolley and McCarter, *Proc. Expt. Biol. Med.*, 1940, 45, 357) for many types of bacteria. So it will be of interest to study whether these quinonoid bodies have any influence on the activity of the sulphanilamides. Further, it has been observed by Gley and Gerard (*Pressa. Med.*, 1936, 42, 1775) that whereas molecular equivalents of prontosil and sulphanilamide are of equal therapeutic potency, the carboxy derivative of prontosil is twice as effective as prontosil, even though molecular proportions of prontosil and its carboxy derivative may give rise only to equal amounts of sulphanilamide. Then again, the azo-dyes prepared from diazotised sulphanilamide with resorcinol, 3 : 5-diaminobenzoic acid, *p*-hydroxyphenylglycine and histidine, pyrrole and indole and some purines (Northey, *Chem. Rev.*, 1940, 27, 85) are reported to be more active than sulphanilamide itself.

A review of the existing literature on the sulphonamide-azo-dyes shows that, though a considerable number of them has been reported, no data of their therapeutic activity is given. Further, only very few azo-dyes of sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine have been studied in detail in respect of their bactericidal activity. It was therefore considered desirable to synthesise a series of azo-dyes of sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine with common phenols and amines which have been found to be effective when coupled with diazotised sulphanilamide.

The results of their pharmacological examination are awaited.

The following azo-dyes have been prepared :

RH Name of phenol (amine) coupled with	TABLE I Azo-dyes derived from sulphathiazole.			Azo-dyes derived from sulphapyridine		
	Colour.	Nitrogen % Found.	% Calc.	Colour.	Nitrogen % Found.	% Calc.
(a) <i>Phenolic azo-dyes</i>						
Phenol	Red	15.69	15.55	Dark red	15.46	15.82
<i>p</i> -Cresol	"	16.23	14.97	" "	16.16	15.23
Resorcinol	"	16.20	14.89	Brick		
Resorcinol mono- methyl ether	Brick red	14.01	14.35	red	15.26	15.14
1 : 2 : 5-Xylenol	Dark red	14.62	14.43	" "	14.36	14.66
Salicylic acid	"	13.69	13.87	" "	14.76	14.51
β -Naphthol	Brown	13.57	13.66	" "	13.87	13.87
α -Naphthol	"	13.54	13.66	" "	13.58	13.87
(b) <i>Aminoazo-dyes</i>						
Dimethylaniline	Dark red	17.74	18.09	Dark red	18.16	18.38
<i>m</i> -Phenylene- diamine	" "	22.71	22.46	" "	22.32	22.83
Anthranilic acid	Yellow	17.20	17.37	Yellow	17.81	17.63
β -Naphthylamine	Dark red	16.91	17.12	Dark red	17.18	17.37
Naphthionic acid	Brick red	13.87	14.37	Brick red	14.39	14.46

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The general procedure adopted for the preparation of phenolic azo-dyes is illustrated in the preparation of the azo-dye derived from diazotised sulphathiazole and phenol.

4-Hydroxy-(p-N¹-2-thiazolyl-sulphamyl).

Sulphathiazole (1 g.) was dissolved in 3 c. c. of 10 % sodium hydroxide and the solution cooled in ice. 10 % Sodium nitrite solution (also well cooled, 5 c.c.) was added with shaking and the resulting mixture cooled to 0°. This was added on to a mixture of 5 c. c. of 10 % HCl and ice, with stirring, when a fine yellow precipitate resulted. This was allowed to stand over with occasional shaking for 15 minutes. Phenol (0.5 g.) was dissolved in 10 c. c. of 10 % sodium hydroxide and cooled to 0° in ice, and the diazonium solution was added on to this with good stirring when a brown-red solution resulted. This was allowed to stand for 2 hours with occasional shaking, and acidified with hydrochloric acid when the dye was precipitated. The dye was purified by dissolving in sodium hydroxide solution and reprecipitating by acidification as red powder, yield 1.2 g.

The general procedure adopted for the preparation of amino-azo dyes is illustrated in the preparation of the *azo-dye* derived from diazotised sulphathiazole and dimethylaniline.

4-Dimethylamino-(p-N¹-2-thiazolyl-sulphamylphenyl-azo)-benzene.

Sulphathiazole (1 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (3 c. c. of 10 %) and cooled in ice. Sodium nitrite solution (5 c. c. of 10 %) was next added with good shaking and the mixture cooled to 0°. This was added on to 5 c. c. of 10 % hydrochloric acid and ice with good stirring and the resulting yellow precipitate was allowed to stand for 15 minutes. Dimethylaniline (0.5 c. c.) was shaken with 2 c. c. of hydrochloric acid (10%) and diluted with water and cooled to 0°. The diazotised sulphathiazole was added on to this with good stirring. A solution of 5 g. of sodium acetate in 10 c. c. of water was added with good shaking and the dark red solution allowed to stand overnight. Next day, the product was made alkaline and the dye was filtered off, washed with water, and purified by dissolving in sodium hydroxide solution and reprecipitating by acidification, yield 1.2 g.